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IMPLANTS WITH PARTIAL AND COMPLETE TOOTH LOSS

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ABSTRACT

One of the most reliable and effective methods of eliminating dental defects in the modern world is dental implantation. Implant placement operations help not only functionally, but also aesthetically restore the integrity of the dentition. Unfortunately, questions about the service life and impact of implants on the bone tissue of the alveolar process of the upper and alveolar part of the lower jaw over time remain relevant today.

Keywords: Bone tissue, crown, cementation, osteoprotegerin, osteoclastogenesis, abutment, implantation.

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ИМПЛАНТАЦИИ С ЧАСТИЧНОЙ И ПОЛНОЙ ПОТЕРЕЙ ЗУБОВ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Одним из самых надежных и эффективных методов устранения дефектов зубных рядов в современном мире является дентальная имплантация. Операции по установке имплантатов помогают не только функционально, но и эстетически восстановить целостность зубного ряда. К сожалению, вопросы о сроках службы и влияния имплантатов на костную ткань альвеолярного отростка верхней и альвеолярной части нижней челюстей с течением времени на сегодняшний день остаются актуальными.

Ключевые слова: костная ткань, коронка, цементация, остеопротегерин, остеокластогенез, абатмент, имплантация.

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ҚИСМАН ВА ТЎЛИҚ ТИШЛАРНИНГ ЙЎҚОЛИШИДА ИМПЛАНТАЦИЯ БАЖАРИШ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Замонавий дунёда тиш нуқсонларини бартараф этишнинг энг ишончли ва самарали усулларида бири бу - тиш имплантациясидир. Имплантларни жойлаштириш операциялари нафақат функционал, балки эстетик жиҳатдан ҳам тишларнинг яхлитлигини тиклашга ёрдам беради. Афсуски, хизмат муддати ва имплантларнинг пастки жағнинг юқори ва алвеоляр қисмидаги алвеоляр жараённинг суяк тўқималарига таъсири ҳақидаги саволлар бугунги кунда ҳам долзарб бўлиб қолмоқда.

Калит сўзлар: суяк тўқимаси, тиш қопламаси, цементация, остеопротегерин, остеокластогенез, абатмент, имплантация.

Relevance of the topic: Today, the most relevant for the patient is the implantation of implants and the duration of their service. There is an opinion among patients that the implant placement is performed once and for life. But, with the passage of time and the patient's age, the condition of bone tissue in the area of the installed implant changes. Also, the patient's state of health does not always change for the better, which can lead to complications and significantly reduce the service life of the prosthesis on artificial supports.

Previously, changes in the state of bone tissue in the area of the installed implant could be detected thanks to X-ray diagnostic methods (such as OPTG, MSCT, CBCT). Accordingly, it was possible to assess the condition of bone tissue only visually. With the progress of technology in X-ray diagnostics, methods have appeared that allow the most reliable determination of the state of bone tissue, for example, CBCT makes it possible to measure bone density in the area of the installed implant.

With the help of X-ray diagnostic methods, it is possible to visually show changes in bone tissue in the area of installed implants.

It is quite difficult to talk about the state of bone tissue without studying the processes that affect its metabolism. In this case, the doctor does not give

the patient is guaranteed the integration and service life of the implant, based only on the examination data and visual changes in the radiograph. To predict the results of implantation, complete information about the general state of health of the patient, and, in particular, about the condition of the bone tissue of the jaws, is necessary.

With a change in the patient's general health status, a number of biochemical parameters that affect resorption and, accordingly, bone tissue restoration in the area of the previously installed implant change, which, unfortunately, are not sufficiently studied.

In addition to visual and diagnostic changes, the present study focuses on biochemical markers of bone metabolism, such as osteoprotegerin and its ligand sRANK-L, whose reference values have not yet been established, as well as the bone isoenzyme alkaline phosphatase with established reference values, which is responsible for the state of bone tissue at the time of the study (i.e., after treatment performed, placement of artificial support, at the time of the patient's treatment). According to PubMed, an English-language text database of medical and biological publications created by the National Center for Biotechnological Information (NCBI) based on the section "biotechnology" of the National Library of Medicine, 23,859 scientific articles by foreign and domestic authors are devoted to bone metabolism disorders. Of these, there are only 9 articles on violations of bone metabolism in dentistry. Specifically, violations of the OPG sRANK-L system are 11 articles. There are no articles devoted to violations of the OPG sRANK-L system in dental implantology.

Examination of the patient's blood serum for osteoprotegerin and its ligand before and after treatment with dental implants will determine the reference values of the indicator. Also, compare these values with the level of the bone isoenzyme alkaline phosphatase in the blood serum, which, in turn, will allow us to assess the condition of bone tissue for the period of the patient's initial treatment. To establish the relationship between changes in bone tissue on CBCT or OPTG images with changes in the level of osteoprotegerin, sRANK-L and bone isoenzyme alkaline phosphatase, which will help to determine the most complete picture of the state of bone tissue of the jaws. These studies will also help predict the outcomes of treatment of dental defects using artificial supports and form further patient management tactics.

Most foreign authors today consider the determination of markers of bone metabolism to be the main diagnostic criterion, without which surgical intervention performed on the bone tissue of the jaws and not only is considered simply impossible. The study of the processes of bone tissue metabolism is the most urgent problem in recent years.

It is impossible to talk about implantation as a new method of replacing dental defects - an increasing number of patients complain about the failure of prostheses on implants due to their long use. The nature of complaints is diverse: from a fracture of the crown part of the prosthesis to the mobility of the entire bridge structure and acute pain in the area of the prosthesis. In general, they can be divided into two groups. The first one is associated with a violation of the orthopedic function of the prosthesis: a screw fracture, a crown chip, a violation of the fit of the crown part to the implant, the appearance of mobility due to mechanical rotation of the locking screw during screw fixation, cementing during cement fixation. Also, during cement fixation, the abutment locking screw may unwind and lack cementing. Treatment tactics for this development are usually limited to replacing the orthopedic structure or restoring it by replacing the abutment locking screw or crown during screw fixation. The second group of complaints is associated with impaired implant function, resorption of bone tissue around the neck and, accordingly, mobility of the entire structure, the addition of pathological processes and a violation of the general metabolism of the body, as a result of which the process of bone remodeling is also disrupted. From a medical point of view, there are a lot of reasons why a prosthesis on artificial supports can fail during use: injuries (fractures of the jaw, fracture of the alveolar process of the upper and alveolar part of the lower jaw, fracture of crowns on implants), poor oral hygiene, changes in the general health of the patient, changes in the immune status. Finding out the causes, identifying complications and determining further management tactics for such patients is an urgent problem and requires immediate solutions to improve the quality of life of patients with prosthetic implants.

The study of changes in the state of bone tissue using biochemical and radiological parameters of bone tissue of the alveolar process of the upper and alveolar part of the lower jaw will help both in predicting the service life of implants and in identifying complications in the process of using implants as artificial supports.

In the long-term period after prosthetics on artificial supports (from 7 to 10 years), approximately 50% of implants of different shapes and sizes disintegrate. If we compare the data on the timing of prosthetics, then by the age of seven to ten, 50% of the supporting teeth are lost. According to the Russian literature [13, 30, 33], the service life of self-supporting bridge prostheses is 5-7 years, and according to foreign data-6-8 years. There is a natural question of what to do in the subsequent period, how to implement the subsequent tactics of managing a patient with dental defects after the loss of a prosthesis.

Some authors believe that after the prosthetics stage, a significant loss of bone tissue gradually begins to occur, especially in 1 year after prosthetics, and by the time the period of 5 years - 7 years is reached, the destruction reaches a level at which the prosthesis becomes untenable and further prosthetics with a fixed orthopedic prosthesis based on implants is impossible. The way out of this situation is the use of removable dentures. However, given the disadvantages of removable structures, the patient returns to change the configuration of the alveolar process of the upper jaw and the alveolar part of the lower jaw. Reconstruction of the alveolar process of the upper jaw and the alveolar part of

the lower jaw is not always possible, since over time not only the clinical situation in the patient's oral cavity changes, but also the general state of health.

The relevance of this topic is also confirmed by research conducted by many authors. These authors prove that biochemical studies are highly informative for determining the state of bone tissue metabolism and justify the choice of management tactics for patients with various pathologies. But, according to some, the values of one indicator are enough to diagnose and determine treatment, while others, on the contrary, say that it is necessary to use several markers to obtain the most reliable information. The quantitative composition of markers of bone metabolism is diverse, and it is extremely difficult to obtain data on each known marker for a particular patient due to the rather long time of such a study, as well as the high cost of reagents for each. This study offers the most informative set of markers of bone metabolism in the average price category, which, according to the authors, in the near future will increase the level of diagnosis to determine further treatment tactics and, consequently, improve the patient's quality of life.

Analysis of domestic and foreign literature has shown that currently the processes occurring at the cellular and intracellular levels are actively studied, however, in the field of dental implantology, there are no studies of osteoclastogenesis processes that would allow us to correctly predict treatment with dental implants, and monitor the state of bone tissue at all stages of treatment with artificial supports, which confirms relevance of this topic.

Purpose of the study: to determine the regularities of changes in the state of bone tissue of the alveolar process of the upper jaw and the alveolar part of the lower jaw in patients with dental implants in the long term to improve the quality of surgical treatment using dental implants.

Research objectives:

1. To determine the dependence of changes in the biochemical parameters of bone metabolism in the alveolar process of the upper and alveolar part of the lower jaw in patients with partial and complete tooth loss.

2. To evaluate changes in the bone tissue of the alveolar process of the upper and alveolar part of the lower jaw in patients with partial and complete tooth loss, using implants as artificial supports using modern diagnostic methods.

3. Establish physiologically acceptable limits of the biochemical parameters OPG and sRANK-L for use as a diagnostic method for dental implantation.

4. To determine the possibility of using biochemical markers of osteoclastogenesis to identify indications for dental implantation and reconstructive interventions on the upper or lower jaw in case of failure of the prosthesis on artificial supports.

Scientific novelty. Changes in bone tissue markers in the blood serum of patients using implants as artificial supports, as well as visual changes during radiography (OPTG and CBCT) were determined.

The physiological boundaries of osteoprotegerin and sRANK-L and their relationships were determined for predicting the results of implantation in the long term, the dynamics of the implant integration process, as well as for expanding the indications for the reuse of artificial supports due to the failure of artificial support prostheses after time has elapsed.

The possibility of restoring the functional and aesthetic integrity of the dentition rows of patients, when the artificial support prosthesis is no longer functional and needs to be removed, was found on the basis of biochemical data, namely, based on the determination of markers of osteoclastogenesis.

Practical significance. Determination of biochemical markers of osteoclastogenesis, as well as their ratios, can be used in predicting the service life of prostheses on implants, monitoring the dynamics of the process of implant integration in bone tissue. The use of these data can be carried out not only at the stage of installation and during the use of the prosthesis, but also when the prosthesis on implants becomes unstable, and will determine the further tactics of patient management.

References.

1. Aghaloo T.L. Controversies in Implant Surgery / Aghaloo T.L., Mardirosian M., Delgado B. / *Oral Maxillofac. Surg. Clin.* — North Am. — 2017. — № 4. — P. 525-535.
2. Bitra A. Gingival Crevicular Fluid Turnover Markers in Premenopausal vs Postmenopausal Women receiving Orthodontic Treatment. / Bitra A., Rani B.J., Agarkar S.S., Parihar A.S., Vynath G.P., Grover S. // *J Contemp. Dent. Pract.* — 2017. — № 18 (10) — P. 933— 936.
3. Biguetti C. Proteomic profiling and differential messenger RNA expression correlate HSP27 and serpin family B member 1 to apical periodontitis outcomes. / Cavalla F., Biguetti C., Jain S., Johnson C., Letra A., Garlet G.P., Silva R.M. // *J Endod.* — 2017. — № 43(9) — P. 1486— 1493.
4. Cannizzaro G. Two or three machined vs roughened surface dental implants loaded immediately supporting total fixed prostheses: 1-year results from a randomised controlled trial. / Cannizzaro G., Gastaldi G., Gherlone E., Vinci R., Loi I., Trullenque-Eriksson A., Esposito M. // *Eur. J. Oral Implantol.* — 2017. — № 10 (3) — P. 279— 291.
5. Chatzopoulos G.S. Implant and endodontic treatment selection are influenced by patients' demographic characteristics, insurance status, and medical history: A retrospective cohort study / Chatzopoulos G.S., Wolff L.F. // *Quintessence Int.* — 2017. — № 48(9) — P. 753—764.
6. De Cremer K. Controlled release of chlorhexidine from a meso-porous silica-containing macroporous titanium dental implant prevents microbial bio film formation. / De Cremer K., Braem A., Gerits E., De Brucker K., Vandamme K., Martens J.A., Michiels J., Vleugels J., Cammue B.P., Thevissen K. // *Eur. Cell Mater.* — 2017. — № 33. — P. 13—27.
7. Ferreira M. Levofloxacin-loaded bone cement delivery system: Highly effective against intracellular bacteria and Staphylococcus aureus bio films / Ferreira M., Rzhepishevskaya O., Grenho L., Malheiros D., Gonfalves L., Almeida A.J., Jordao L., Ribeiro I.A., Ramstedt M., Gomes P., Bettencourt A. // *Int J Pharm.* — 2017. — № 532(1) — P. 241—248.
8. Fabris A.L.D.S. Morphometric and histologic characterization of alveolar bone from hypertensive patients / Fabris A.L.D.S., Mulinari-Santos G., Hassumi J.S., Freire A.R., Faverani L.P., Gruber R., Okamoto R. // *Clin. Implant Dent. Relat. Res.* — 2017. — <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/29034574>
9. Guobis Z. General diseases influence on peri-implantitis development: a systematic review / Guobis Z., Pacauskiene I., Astramskaite I. // *J Oral Maxillofac. Res.* — 2016. — № 7(3) — P.5.
10. Krennmair S. Factors affecting peri-implant bone resorption in four Implant supported mandibular full-arch restorations: a 3-year prospective study. / Krennmair S., Weinländer M., Forstner T., Krennmair G., Stimmelmayer M. // *J Clin. Periodontol.* — 2016. — № 43(1) — P. 92—101.
11. Lee K. Distribution of medical status and medications in elderly patients treated with dental implant surgery covered by national healthcare insurance in Korea / Lee K., Dam C., Huh J., Park K.M., Kim S.Y., Park W. // *J Dent. Anesth. Pain Med.* — 2017. — № 17(2). — P. 113— 119.
12. Liu J. Gallium and silicon synergistically promote osseointegration of dental implant in patients with osteoporosis / Liu J, Wu Z, He H, Cai K, Zhang H, Xu L. // *Med Hypotheses.* — 2017. — № 103. — P. 35—38.
13. Mardas N. Guided bone regeneration in osteoporotic conditions following treatment with zoledronic acid. / Mardas N., Busetti J., de Figueiredo J.A., Mezzomo L.A., Scarparo R.K., Donos N. // *Clin. Oral Implants Res.* — 2017. — № 28(3). — P. 362—371.
14. Mardas N. Guided bone regeneration in osteoporotic conditions following treatment with zoledronic acid /Mardas N., Busetti J., de Figueiredo J.A., Mezzomo L.A., Scarparo R.K., Donos N. // *Clin. Oral Implants Res.* — 2017. — № 28(3) — P. 362—371.
15. Okamoto K. Osteoimmunology: The Conceptual Framework Unifying the Immune and Skeletal Systems / Okamoto K., Nakashima T., Shinohara M., Negishi-Koga T., Komatsu N.,

- Terashima A., Sawa S., Nitta T., Takayanagi H. // *Physiol. Rev.* — 2017. — № 97(4) — P. 1295-1349.
16. Sayardoust S. Clinical, radiological, and gene expression analyses in smokers and non-smokers, Part 2: RCT on the late healing phase of osseointegration /Sayardoust S., Omar O., Norderyd O., Thomsen P. // *Clin. Implant Dent. Relat. Res.* — 2017. — № 19(5) — P. 901—915.
17. Trawitzki B.F. Low-intensity laser therapy efficacy evaluation in mice subjected to acute arthritis condition / Trawitzki B.F., Lilge L., de Figueiredo F.A.T., Macedo A.P., Issa J.P.M. / *J Photochem Photobiol B.* — 2017. — № 174.— P. 126—132.
18. Tatullo M. Bone inflammation, bone infection and dental implants failure: Histological and Cytological Aspects Related to Cement Excess /Tatullo M., Marrelli M., Mastrangelo F., Gherlone E. // *J Bone Jt. Infect.* — 2017. — Vol. 2(2). — P. 84— 89.
19. Yang D.H. Preparation and evaluation of dexamethasone (DEX)/Growth and differentiation factor-5 (GDF-5) surface-modified titanium using P-Cyclodextrin-conjugated heparin (CD-Hep) for enhanced osteogenic activity in vitro and in vivo / Yang D.H., Yoon S.J., Lee D.W. / *Int J Mol. Sci.* — 2017. — № 18(8) // <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/28771196>.
20. Yamauchi R. Photofunctionalised Ti6Al4V implants enhance early phase osseointegration /Yamauchi R., Itabashi T., Wada K., Tanaka T., Kumagai G., Ishibashi Y. // *Bone Joint Res.* — 2017 — № 6(5) — P. 331—336.

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